

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF SUPPLEMENTAL INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS IN LINEAR INEQUALITIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11627092>

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to develop and validate the Supplemental Instructional Materials Module in Linear Inequalities in Mathematics 8 based on the Least Mastered Competencies for the Second Quarter of Grade 8 learners at Buenavista National High School and Cabong National High School. Two hundred sixty-five learners participated in this study. A survey questionnaire was distributed to the Grade 8 learners in the two public schools of Buenavista District I. The Supplemental Instructional Materials were developed and validated by the four (4) Masters Teachers. In terms of validity of contents, equity and accessibility, instructional design and support, assessment, presentations and organization, and replicability, having a composite mean of 4.25, all these ratings are considered outstanding. Based on the data it was concluded that the enhanced Supplemental Instructional Materials was developed, and all the parts met its validity. Based on the findings and conclusion, it is highly recommended that administrator's curriculum planners, educators, and teachers be allowed to use the developed learning materials. Learners may also use the learning materials as a guide in Quarter 2 in Mathematics 8. Moreover, future researchers may also use the study findings as a reference in crafting and developing learning materials.

Keywords: *Mathematics 8, Linear Inequalities, Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM)*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is considered one of the most complicated academic disciplines in school settings. The diversified nature of problem-solving taught in secondary

education is difficult for many students worldwide, including those in the Philippines. Nowadays, mathematics education tries to build the capacity for investigation, hypothesis formation, logical thinking organization, non-routine problem solving, and the establishing of linkages between mathematical concepts, and other intellectual domains. Mathematics is an essential component of education and is necessary at all curriculum levels. As a result, this subject necessitates intense mental focus and logical thinking. People considered mathematics to be a challenging topic. Many students perform poorly in Mathematics and find the subject very challenging.

According to Antiporda (2014), learners' performance in Mathematics at the end of secondary education has not improved over the last decade. This assertion is corroborated by the National Achievement Test (NAT) performance of the country's high schools, which fell from 50.7% in the 2007-2008 school year to 46.3% in the 2011-2012 school year, as well as its low ranking of 115th out of 142 states in the Global Competitiveness Report. Furthermore, according to international test results such as the 2003 TIMSS (Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study), the Philippines placed 34th out of 38 nations in HS II Math. Similarly, 2008 data reveal that even with only the Science high schools competing in the Advanced Mathematics category, the Philippines ranked last (Department of Education 2010).

According to the PISA (2018) findings, the Philippines placed last out of 79 participating nations, with mathematics being second to bottom. Unfortunately, at least 78% of students in the Philippines did not meet the minimum competency standards in each of the three PISA courses. Only 19% met the minimal competency level for overall Mathematics outcomes. This emphasizes the critical need to reform the country's education system and create more possibilities for pupils to succeed.

During the Buenavista District I school-based Numeracy Test, the total test results declined by 5% compared to 2022. In the school year 2022-2023, the result declined depending on the percentage of the test, and it did not meet the objective passing percentage of at least 75%.

In response to the perceived needs of the education sector, the Department of Education (DepEd) has continued to advocate for changes to the primary education curriculum. The establishment of Republic Act No. 10533 prepared the ground introducing of K-12 education in the Philippines. However, implementing the curriculum is challenging, mainly when teaching Junior High School Mathematics, because the K-12 curriculum employs a spiral progression strategy across courses. Learners should be educated about topics ranging from elementary to complicated. The spiral progression technique is intended to build on the same principles at each grade level and advance in complexity from kindergarten to Grade 10 (DepEd Order 21 S. 2019; Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013). Furthermore, skipping the core topics in mathematics will result in low academic performance. Many students had to deal with these challenges, contributing to poor performance across all areas.

Firestone (2016) stated that when learners are given the assistance they require while learning something new, they have a better probability of employing that knowledge independently, and mastery and retention of the concepts, and abilities are guaranteed.

Furthermore, the emphasis on instruction is on providing teachers with the resources they need to help students build cognitive learning skills. Estacio (2015) explains that the teaching-learning process "depends on how the goals are attained at the end of the process, and thus the realization of these goals relies on the teacher who chooses the right methodology, and strategy, which are relevant instructional materials and valid and reliable assessment tools." It promotes student learning, which leads to improved performance and achievement. Furthermore, instructional materials must reflect students' interests, knowledge, understanding, abilities, needs, and experiences. When offering quality education, one should not overstate the importance of instructional materials in effective instruction. Aside from the introductory textbook, using instructional materials is essential for meaningful and effective teaching".

As a result, the Department of Education (DepEd) released a statement advising that schools strengthen the competencies required to improve the performance of all students across the country. One of the recommendations is to provide materials to improve school competencies (DepEd Order No. 39, 2012). SIM is a remedial tool that assists students at their current knowledge level, enhancing their academic performance. Similarly, DepEd Order No. 08, Series of urges teachers to implement remediation when students are already struggling in a subject, as evidenced by low ratings in any learning area. Studies from Asian countries that applied Supplemental Instructional Materials to know how effective implementing these interventions are, but these are limited only in context, number of participants, respondents, the variables included in the study, and the methodology in teaching in which this study was made. Arpilleda (2021) emphasizes that SIM, a well-structured and thoroughly organized piece of content, will help students who do not have a firm grasp of the idea overcome such issues.

According to Bandang and Parangat (2022), most of the teachers developed a variety of intervention items for pupils who struggled with math. In remedial sessions, Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM focuses on the learners' least-mastered mathematics skills. It is a learning tool that assists students in mastering competency-based abilities not often taught in the classroom.

To increase students' mathematical skills, math teachers must be original, imaginative, and creative while producing strategic intervention materials.

It is a resource available to students to help them learn and master competency-based skills that they could not gain through traditional classroom instruction. SIM is a comprehensive technique that assists students, particularly those underperforming in becoming self-directed and productive learners. SIM evaluations will most likely use a variety of approaches to allow students to demonstrate their learning through task performance and application to real-world circumstances. (SIMs) are intended to help professors provide students with the motivation to excel in their courses (Sinco et al.,2020).

Furthermore, extra instructional materials required pupils to satisfy defined competency standards while developing lifelong learning skills. The purpose of this study is to determine the extent to which activities contribute to the development of mathematical competence.

The biggest challenge for teachers is to improve their students' performance in mathematics. The mathematics department at Buenavista National High School is now hosting the researcher, whose goal is to reduce the proportion of students who perform poorly in mathematics. To make it possible, Mathematics teachers conducted a numeracy test last school year, and yielded poor results. Strategic intervention material was currently used by the Mathematics Department to improve the poor performance of learners in mathematics. The outcomes of these projects did not meet the targeted percentage, so the researcher ought to develop supplemental instructional materials. She came up with this study to improve the academic performance of the grade 8 learners in mathematics, specifically in the Second Quarter of the school year, so the researcher comes up with identified the least mastered competencies for the last three consecutive years to develop new supplemental instructional materials and validated by the experts.

Research Questions

This research aimed to determine the Development and Validation of the Supplemental Instructional Materials Module on Linear Inequality. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the least mastered competencies identified based on the Trends Analysis for the last five years?
2. What are the difficulties encountered by the Grade 8 learners in mastering the learning competencies in Mathematics 8 in Linear Inequalities?
3. What Supplemental Instructional Materials can be developed based on the Identified Least Mastered Competencies specifically in Linear Inequalities?
4. What is the level of validity of Supplemental Instructional Materials as assessed by the validators in terms of:
 - 4.1 Content
 - 4.2 Equity and Accessibility
 - 4.3 Assessment
 - 4.4 Presentation and Organization
 - 4.5 Instructional Design and Support
 - 4.6 Replicability?
5. What are the recommendations given by the validators to improve the Supplemental Instructional Materials?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter elucidated the methodologies and protocols that enable the researcher to carry out the study effectively. This chapter focused on various aspects of the research study, including the research design, research locale, research population and sampling, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and statistical treatment.

Research Design

This study used descriptive research methodologies, both quantitative and qualitative. Identifying patterns based on the least learned competencies from prior years. We made a SIM based on the patterns in Numeracy Test Results. The SIM was validated to see whether learners improved their performance regarding the least learned competencies in Mathematics 8, specifically the Linear Inequalities in Two Variables lesson.

The researcher developed and validated Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) since the previous SIM did not successfully meet the target percentage. The researcher used the least mastered competencies based on trends encompassing the second quarter of Grade 8 learners' Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) as defined by the Department of Education. The produced extra instructional materials will be reviewed and validated by the mathematics department's master teachers and a school principal. This study gathered data from prior years' least mastered competencies results. Respondents identified the obstacles experienced in the learning skills and validated the development of extra instructional materials.

Research Locale Population and Sampling

The study focuses on two types of respondents. The first group includes professionals who will validate the materials. The second group of respondents are the public schools in Buenavista Quezon's District 1 for the 2023-2024 school year. The researcher focused solely on all grade 8 students in all public schools in Buenavista District 1 who participated in this study.

The study includes all 265 grade 8 students, or 100% of the population, currently enrolled in Buenavista National High School and Cabong National High School.

This purposive sampling method enabled the researcher to gather valuable insights and data relevant to the research objectives while facilitating the development of Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) anchored to the specific needs of Grade 8 learners in the public schools of Buenavista, District 1.

The Population of the Study

Name of Schools	The population of Grade 8 Learners	Percentage
Buenavista National High School	237	89.43%
Cabong National High School	28	10.57%
Total Number	265	100%

Research Instrument

The researcher developed and validated Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) in response to the critical challenges of secondary schools in District 1, namely the least taught abilities in Mathematics 8. The primary research tool used in this study is a Teacher-Constructed for Trend Analysis Data Retrieval and Secondary Data Analysis of 5 years of Item Analysis Results to comprehensively evaluate the least mastered competencies of Grade 8 learners in Mathematics 8, specifically in the Second Quarter. To assure the validity and reliability of the Item Analysis, a comprehensive validation method was used.

It is critical to note that Trend Analysis Data Retrieval is an accurate method for identifying the least mastered competencies. Each standard in the curriculum guide determines the distribution of topics on the exam, ensuring a thorough and competency-based evaluation.

Five-point Likert Rating Scale Interpretation

Scale	Range Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 - 5.00	Always Encountered (AE)	Learners are consistently encountered in their learning competencies in Mathematics 8. They always encountered difficulties that lead to least mastered competencies of Grade 8 learners.
4	3.40 – 4.19	Often Encountered (OE)	Learners are regularly encountered in their learning competencies in Mathematics 8

3	2.60 – 3.39	Sometimes Encountered (SE)	Learners are frequently encountered in their learning competencies in Mathematics 8. They sometimes encountered difficulties that lead to least mastered competencies of Grade 8 learners.
2	1.80 – 2.59	Rarely Encountered (RE)	Learners are seldom encountered in their learning competencies in Mathematics 8. They rarely encountered difficulties that lead to least mastered competencies of Grade 8 learners.
1	1.00 – 1.79	Never Encountered (NE)	Learners are least encountered in their learning competencies in Mathematics 8. They never encountered difficulties that lead to least mastered competencies of Grade 8 learners.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researcher's primary tool for gathering the necessary data and information for problem-solving is the least mastered competencies based on the previous year's patterns.

In this study, the researcher used a Teacher-Constructed Trend Analysis Data Retrieval explicitly intended to examine the least learned competencies in Mathematics 8 during the second quarter of the school year.

Following completion, the responses were encoded. These results were combined and analyzed using the item analysis algorithm to provide a complete picture of the student's performance in Mathematics 8. This analysis not only evaluates their overall performance but also identifies learning gaps and areas of Grade 8 students.

Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) were created based on a trend analysis of the least mastered competencies. After producing (SIM) the materials are validated by the master's teachers. To ensure its reliability and validity, it is related to how consistent and trustworthy the study is, ensuring that these materials will undoubtedly be validated by school principals and master teachers. The goal is to ensure that the study does not produce inconsistent outcomes.

For ethical considerations, a letter was noted by the Dean and adviser requesting the endorsement of the undertaking. Upon approval, the researcher will seek permission from the principal and discuss the process of the conduct of the study.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM) were generated using a trend analysis of the least mastered competencies. After completing (SIM), the researcher validated by professionals, to ensure its reliability and validity, considering how consistent and trustworthy the study is, as these materials will almost certainly be validated by school principals and master instructors. The goal is to ensure that the study yields consistent results. The study's validity was determined by how well it measured what it was intended to measure. Trends Analysis Data Retrieval results are conveyed to data users using Mean Percentage Scores (MPS) and descriptive equivalent for data utilization to create Supplemental Instructional Materials (SIM). Specified below is the mastery level:

Legend	Descriptive Equivalent
96%-100%	Mastered
86%-95%	Closely Approx. Mastery
66%-85%	Moving toward Mastery
35%-65%	Average
16%-34%	Low
5%-15%	Very Low
0%-4%	No Mastery

The data on challenges or issues were evaluated using a survey questionnaire to identify the kind of difficulties that the learners encountered.

The table below is used to evaluate the data collected from the Validity survey, which was validated by an expert.

Scale for the Evaluation Criterion for SIM Validation

Mean Interval	Verbal Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Outstanding
3.40 – 4.19	Very Satisfactory
2.60 – 3.39	Satisfactory
1.80 – 2.59	Less Satisfactory
1.00 – 1.79	Unsatisfactory

RESULTS

Part I. The Least Mastered Competencies

Additionally, solving problems involving linear inequalities in two variables (LC3) also presents the decreasing of mean percentage score 20,19,16,15 and 13 from low mastery to a very low mastery that leads the topic to least mastered competency. Solving problems involving linear inequalities requires strong algebraic skills, such as manipulating equations, simplifying expressions, and solving equations. Learners with weak algebraic skills may struggle to apply these skills effectively in solving problems involving linear inequalities.

Likewise, solves problems involving systems of linear inequalities in two variables (LC4) gained the decreasing of mean percentage score of (25,17,17,15 and 12) that leads the topic to a very low mastery. Understanding how to graph and interpret systems of linear inequalities on a coordinate plane can be challenging. Learners may struggle with accurately plotting the lines and shading the correct regions to represent the solution set. By addressing these difficulties and employing effective learning strategies, learners can improve their performance and achieve a higher mean percentage score in solving problems involving systems of linear inequalities in two variables.

In addition, the rest learning competencies of the second quarter gained from average to closely approaching mastery leads to the learners fully understanding the

topics. Mastery involves building upon prior knowledge and making connections between different mathematical topics. Understanding the interconnectedness of mathematical concepts promotes a holistic understanding and facilitates the acquisition of new knowledge. Mastery in mathematics requires a deep understanding of fundamental concepts and principles. It involves going beyond superficial knowledge and developing a thorough comprehension of mathematical ideas and their interconnections.

This study has highlighted the least learned competencies from the last five years, indicating where learners struggle and need additional support. This decline may also be influenced by the quality of academic performances impacted by these challenges.

Table 1

Identified Most Trends of Least Mastered Competencies in Mathematics 8 during the Second Quarter of the School Year: 2019-2024.

Second Quarter	Content Standards	Performance Standards	Identified Most Trends of Least Mastered Competencies in Grade 8 Mathematics in Second Quarter (SY. 2019-2024)
2	Demonstrates key concepts of linear inequalities in two variables, systems of linear inequalities in two variables, and linear functions.	Formulate and solve accurately real-life problems involving linear inequalities in two variables, systems of linear inequalities in two variables, and linear functions.	Illustrates and graphs linear inequalities in two variables.
			solves problems involving linear inequalities in two variables.
			solves problems involving systems of linear inequalities in two variables.
			determines dependent and independent variables.
			graphs and illustrates a linear function and its (a) domain; (b) range; (c) table of values; (d) intercepts; and (e) slope.
			determines the relationship between the hypothesis and the conclusion of an if-then statement.
	Demonstrates understanding of key concepts of logic and reasoning.	Communicate mathematical thinking with coherence and clarity in formulating and analyzing arguments	determines the inverse, converse, and contrapositive of an if-then statement.
			illustrates the equivalences of (a) the statement and its contrapositive; and (b) the converse and inverse of a statement.
			uses inductive or deductive reasoning in an argument.
			writes a proof (both direct and indirect).

Table 1 depicts the identified least mastered competencies in Mathematics 8 during the second quarter of the 2019-2024 school year, as supported by Gosselin (2014), the lowest level of applied skills and knowledge that should enable learners to successfully function in educational and other life situations. According to the statistics provided, the majority of the least mastered competencies in the second quarter are linear inequalities between two variables. Identifying the reasons for the least mastered competencies is critical. It enables focused interventions, differentiated instruction, and the development of methods to address the individual issues that students experience. Addressing these factors will provide learners with the support and opportunities to deepen their mastery of their abilities. According to Toquero (2020), SIMs have evolved into teacher assistance materials that assist students in mastering least-learned competencies.

Through this, the study developed and validated supplemental materials to give learners extra practice opportunities to reinforce their understanding of mathematical concepts. Through repeated practice, learners can strengthen their skills and improve their proficiency in the least mastered competencies.

According to Suarez and Casinillo (2020), materials are intended to support teachers and educators in effectively teaching and supporting students in learning various subjects or skills. It is important to note that while supplemental instructional materials can be beneficial, they should be used in conjunction with regular classroom instruction and teacher guidance. Teachers should provide guidance, monitor progress, and ensure that the materials align with the curriculum and learning objectives. By combining the use of supplemental materials with effective teaching strategies, teachers can address the least mastered competencies of students more comprehensively and effectively.

Part II. Difficulties Encountered by the Grade 8 Learners in Learning Competencies in Mathematics 8.

Table 2

Difficulties Encountered by the Grade 8 Learners in Learning Competencies in Mathematics 8 in the Second Quarter

I. Formulate and solve accurately real-life problems involving linear inequalities in two variables, Systems of linear inequalities in two variables, and linear functions."						Mean Adjectival Rank			
	5	4	3	2	1	Rating			
1. Confused in identifying linear inequality symbols.	132	97	20	7	9	4.27	AE	2	
2. Lack of ability to visualize graphs in linear inequalities in two variables.	115	85	32	12	21	3.98	OE	4	

3. Difficulties in solving problems involving linear inequalities in two variables.	125	79	40	9	12	4.12	AE	3
4. Weakness in understanding the concept of solving problems involving systems of linear inequalities in two variables.	154	82	20	5	4	4.42	AE	1
5. Struggling on how to construct graphs and illustrate a linear function and its (a) domain; (b) range; (c) table of values; (d) intercepts; and (e) slope.	128	55	32	14	36	3.85	OE	5
6. Misconception of identifying the relationship between the hypothesis and the conclusion of an if-then statement.	155	23	21	26	30	3.82	OE	6
II. Communicate mathematical thinking with coherence and clarity in formulating and analyzing arguments.								
7. Struggles in understanding the concept of the inverse, converse, and contrapositive of an if-then statement.	34	76	65	44	46	3.03	SE	8
8. Difficulty in analyzing the equivalences of (a) the statement and its contrapositive; and (b) the converse and inverse of a statement.	45	34	58	79	49	2.80	SE	9
9. Lack of understanding of the concept of inductive and deductive reasoning.	57	48	20	21	119	2.63	SE	10
10. Weak conceptual understanding in writing a proof (both direct and indirect).	41	66	82	25	51	3.08	SE	7
Composite Mean						3.61	OE	

Legend:

4.20 - 5.00	Always Encountered (AE)
3.40 - 4.19	Often Encountered (OE)
2.60 - 3.39	Sometimes Encountered (SE)
1.80 - 2.59	Rarely Encountered (RE)
1.00 - 1.79	Never Encountered (NE)

Table 2 displays the outcomes of the issues the students encountered. As a result, the most common difficulty they experienced, with a mean percentage score of 4.42, was understanding the notion of solving problems involving systems of linear

inequalities in two variables. The concept of systems of linear inequalities in two variables might be esoteric and difficult to grasp. Students may fail to comprehend how the inequalities are depicted. Students may struggle if they have not yet mastered these.

This confusion can cause students who have not mastered these core math abilities to suffer. Additionally, learners failed to recognize linear inequality symbols, with a mean score of 4.27. This suggests that students frequently become confused among the numerous inequality symbols, especially the 'greater than or equal to' (\geq) and 'less than or equal to' (\leq) symbols. This confusion can lead to mistakes in interpreting and solving inequalities.

Furthermore, difficulties in solving problems involving linear inequalities in two variables exceed the learners' "Always Encountered" mean score of 4.12. The learners frequently had difficulty visualizing graphs with linear inequalities in two variables, with a mean score of 3.98. Struggling with how to construct graphs and illustrate a linear function and its (a) domain; (b) range; (c) table of values; (d) intercepts; and (e) slope? With a mean score percentage of 3.85, this means that understanding and applying these concepts necessitates a solid understanding of the underlying mathematics. Learners may struggle to comprehend these abstract concepts, particularly if they lack a strong foundation in mathematics or have not yet established good spatial reasoning skills.

Finally, the misconception of identifying the relationship between the hypothesis and the conclusion of an if-then statement exceeds a mean score of 3.82, understanding the concept of the inverse, converse, and contrapositive of an if-then statement mean score of 3.03, analyzing the equivalences of (a) the statement and its contrapositive; and (b) the converse and inverse of a statement (2.80), understanding of the concept of inductive and deductive reasoning (2.63).

Part III. Supplemental Instructional Materials Developed

The materials were created to help students grasp the Second Quarter's least learned competencies, which are linear inequalities in two variables. Supplemental instructional materials can provide additional support, enrichment, and differentiation to help students learn more effectively. Students' learning is greatly aided when the teacher teaches at the appropriate pace. A teacher who has advanced in their chosen field of specialization is characterized by his ability to organize and design curriculum materials appropriate for the student's level of preparation and understanding. These materials are great resources for promoting deeper comprehension, engagement, and motivation, which leads to better educational outcomes.

Part IV. Validity of the Developed Supplemental Instructional Materials

Table 3 *Validity of Supplemental Instructional Materials*

Criteria	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Content	4.08	VS
Equity and Accessibility	4.08	VS
Assessment	4.25	O
Organization and Presentation	4.42	O
Instructional Design and Support	4.08	VS
Replicability	4.60	O
Composite Mean	4.25	O

Legend:

4.20-5.00	Outstanding (O)
3.40-4.19	Very Satisfactory (VS)
2.60-3.39	Satisfactory (S)
1.80-2.59	Less Satisfactory (LS)
1.00-1.79	Unsatisfactory (U)
12-20 as the total score	Passed

The supplemental Instructional Materials in Grade 8 Mathematics were evaluated and validated by four (4) Junior Schools Master Teachers in content, equity, and accessibility, assessment, organization and presentation, instructional design and support, and replicability.

Based on Table 3, among the six criteria, Replicability got the highest mean score of 4.60. It revealed that the SIM obtained consistent results. Regarding organization and presentation, the developed materials are valid and supported by a mean score of 4.42. It means that the lessons are clear, understandable, and interactive so that the learners can acquire new skills.

Moreover, the assessment of the developed Supplemental Instructional Materials got a mean score of 4.25 and was described as very satisfactory, which explained that the assessment of the materials is suited and appropriate to the learners and meets the targeted learning objectives.

In terms of content, equality and accessibility, and instructional design and support, all these categories received the same mean score of 4.08, indicating that the lessons' material is linked with the curriculum and that learners are engaged in higher-ordered thinking abilities. Similarly, the equality and accessibility of the lessons make

it easy for learners to adapt the lessons to the school's learning resources. Finally, instructional design and support are super, indicating that the resources are well-organized and appropriate for the learners.

Part V. Recommendation of the Validators

Based on the validators' comments and ideas, make a recommendation to enhance and improve the materials. Validator 1 suggested adding visuals to draw the learner's attention to the information. However, the images should be relevant, acceptable, and serve the learning objectives. Images should complement the text rather than distract or overwhelm learners. Accessibility should be carefully considered, to ensure that resources are inclusive and accessible to students with visual impairments and other disabilities.

Validator 2 recommended correct formatting and consistency with font style, size, and spacing. Consistent formatting makes the text clear and easy to read. Appropriate font size and spacing between letters, words, and lines improve readability, allowing learners to understand the text better and creating a visual hierarchy within the contents. Headings, subheadings, and sections can be distinguished by font size, style, or space, allowing students to quickly identify and navigate the information easily. This organizing structure enhances general knowledge and ease of usage. Validator 3 recommended revising the directions/procedures to offer clear and concise instructions that are simple to follow. This clarity helps learners better understand the task requirements, eliminating confusion and doubt. Finally, Validator 4 recommended including some engaging activities. Engaging activities draw students' attention and pique their interest, making the learning process more pleasurable and inspiring. When students are interested and motivated, they are more likely to interact with the materials and invest in their education.

These recommendations are relevant to improve the materials and to help learners struggling in mathematics 8.

DISCUSSION

The following are the findings of the study:

This research aimed to determine the Development and Validation of the Supplemental Instructional Materials Module on Linear Inequality Least mastered competencies are identified based on the Trends Analysis for the last 5 years.

1. According to the trends in performance for the last five years of Grade 8 learners, there are specific competencies in Mathematics 8 that the learners struggled with, particularly linear inequalities in two variables, which require effort to master.

2. Difficulties encountered by the Grade 8 learners in mastering the learning competencies in Mathematics 8.

The Grade 8 students struggled with linear inequalities in two variables, explicitly addressing the inequalities. One of the difficulties encountered by the

students is understanding the notion of solving problems involving systems of linear inequalities in two variables, with the highest mean score of 4.42. Identifying linear inequalities symbol with a mean score of 4.27. Difficulties handling problems with linear inequalities in two variables, with a mean score of 4.12. Visualizing graphs with linear inequalities in two variables, with a mean score of 3.98. The learners are struggling to create graphs that depict a linear function and its (a) domain, (b) range, (c) table of values, (d) intercepts, and (e) slope with a mean score percentage of 3.85. Lastly, the misconception of identifying the relationship between the hypothesis and the conclusion of an if-then statement exceeds a mean score of 3.82, understanding the concept of the inverse, converse, and contrapositive of an if-then statement mean score of 3.03, analyzing the equivalences of (a) the statement and its contrapositive; and (b) the converse and inverse of a statement (2.80), understanding of the concept of inductive and deductive reasoning (2.63).

3. Supplemental Instructional Materials are developed based on the least mastered competencies.

To address the least mastered competencies and difficulties encountered by the Grade 8 learners, supplemental instructional material was developed. First, the most identified least mastered competencies were identified, educators can tailor their instruction and support to meet the unique needs of learners, promote greater learning outcomes, and foster more inclusive and effective learning strategies. Likewise, allows educators to address the specific needs of each student, regardless of their starting point, and provide opportunities for academic success and to provide an appropriate activity that can help the learners easily understand the topic. Specifically, the difficulties in solving linear inequalities in two variables, and additionally, solving word problems that involve real-life situations allows learners to apply their knowledge in their everyday lives.

Second, understanding the difficulties learner s encounter in math informs curriculum development and revision. It helps identify areas that require more attention, adjustments, or alternative approaches to ensure that the curriculum meets the needs of all learners.

3. The validity of Strategic Intervention Materials (SIM) in terms of:

3.1 Content The validity is “Very Satisfactory” with a mean percentage of 4.08.

3.2 Equity and Accessibility the validity is “Very Satisfactory” with a mean percentage of 4.08.

3.3 Assessment the validity is “Outstanding” with a mean percentage of 4.25.

3.4 Presentation and Organization the validity is “Outstanding” with a mean percentage of 4.42.

3.5 Instructional Design and Support the validity is “Very Satisfactory” with a mean percentage of 4.08.

Overall, the composite mean score of the validated SIM is 4.25, which means these materials passed the six criteria.

4. Recommendations given by the validators.

Most of the validators provide a recommendation to enhance and improve the materials. The validators suggested inputting more images to attract the learner's attention to the materials, the proper formatting and consistency of the font style, size, and spacing, and revising the directions/procedures on task and more engaging

activities. These recommendations are relevant to improve the materials and to help learners struggling in mathematics 8.

Conclusions

Below are the conclusions based on the findings of the study.

1. The results of the least mastered competencies of Grade 8 learners indicate that there are specific competencies that need to be addressed to gain valuable insights into the competencies that learners have consistently struggled with. This analysis can inform targeted strategies and improvements to enhance student learning and address areas of weakness.
2. By thoroughly analyzing the difficulties encountered by the Grade 8 learners in mathematics. Based on the overall mean percentage score, learners struggled more with understanding and solving the linear inequalities in two variables. By addressing the difficulties, we gain a deeper understanding of the challenges learners face and develop effective strategies to support their learning.
3. In summary, developing supplemental instructional materials plays vital role in enhancing learning, supporting differentiation, promoting personalized learning, addressing gaps, and fostering engagement among learners. These materials provide valuable resources and support to educators and learners, ultimately contributing to improved educational outcomes.
4. Based on criteria of content, equity and accessibility, assessment, presentation and organization, instructional design and support, and replicability, the criterion for validating supplemental instructional materials involves a thorough evaluation to ensure that the materials meet specific standards and criteria. Overall, the mean percentage of 4.25 validated materials for all six criteria. By conducting a comprehensive analysis based on the validation criteria, we can ensure that the supplemental instructional materials meet the required standards and effectively support teaching and learning.
5. Most of the validators provide a recommendation to enhance and improve the materials.

Recommendations of the validators help ensure the quality of the validated math materials. By identifying areas for improvement or enhancement, recommendations contribute to refining the materials, making them more accurate, relevant, and effective in supporting student learning.

The validators suggested inputting more images to attract the learner's attention to the materials, the proper formatting and consistency of the font style, size, and spacing, and revising the directions/procedures on task and more engaging activities. These recommendations are relevant to improve the materials and to help learners struggling in mathematics.

Lastly, as a result of these studies the utilization of these materials can be used as a basis for the lesson in the Second Quarter of Mathematics 8. These modules are

designed to guide both teachers and learners through a series of lessons and activities that build on each other, promoting a progressive understanding of mathematical concepts in mathematics 8. Modules are often aligned with the curriculum standards and learning objectives. They help ensure that the content covered in the modules aligns with the specific grade-level expectations and educational standards.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations as a result of offered:

1. Since the study developed and validated supplemental instructional material specifically in linear inequalities in two variables, administrators and curriculum planners may allow the use of the developed materials in improving Mathematics instructions.

2. Based on the findings, the content validity of the developed learning materials is very valid, thus educators and teachers may use this as an alternative material in teaching Linear Inequalities in Two Variables.

3. The materials are designed to make it easy to understand and could also develop the higher critical thinking needed for life-long learning for learners. Thus, the students may use these learning materials as a guide in Mathematics 8 lessons specifically in Linear Inequalities in Two Variables.

4. Findings of this study may be used by future researchers in conducting similar research or may be used as a reference in crafting and developing Supplemental Instructional Materials in other subject areas.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study ensured the informed consent was given to the following respondents. Freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interests exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

Acknowledgments

The researcher wishes to express his heartfelt gratitude to the persons with wholehearted cooperation, support and guidance, especially to all who extended contribution and assistance in various ways towards the completion of this study and make this a reality.

Foremost, our GOD ALMIGHTY, the provider and source of all enlightenment and power, for giving his knowledge, perseverance, hope and determination to make his study possible.

To Marinduque State College President Dr. Diosdado P. Zulueta, for his leadership and selfless assistance when needed;

Dr. Leodegario M. Jalos, Jr., Chairperson of Extended Graduate Programs of Marinduque State College, for his untiring support, technical assistance and continuous guidance to the researcher in order for this study to be a success;

Dean of Graduate Studies of Quezonian Educational College, Inc. Dr. Rizalie M. Lim, for her encouragement and moral support for seeing this research through the end;

Dr. Noel R. Palomares, her adviser, for his valuable suggestions, guidance and patience in checking this paper and for the enlightenment shared about the importance of this study;

Engr. Willer A. Dayahan and Mr. Renante S. Camay, for their generously contributing time and expertise of this study as statistician;

Dr. Annalyn J. Decena, for constructing the structure of research as a grammarian and editor;

Ms. Annie M. Ruiz, for constructing the structure of research as copy editor;

Members of the defense panel Dr. Diosdado P. Zulueta, Dr. Julieta Q. Nabos, and Dr. Rogel L. Limpiada for their pertinent comments and advice on how to make the study better;

Ms. Liezl M. Manoy; MSC's Support Staff, Graduate School, for her unending moral support;

Grade 8 learners of Buenavista National High School and Cabong National High School, for actively participating in the conduct of study;

Ms. Angelaine C. Escolano, Ms Janice Irish O. Hernandez, and Mrs. Karen Ruth M. Rodriguez, for their unending support and understanding to finish this study;

Mrs. Alden B. Cuales, her parent, and her siblings, Noela B. Cuales and Clifford B. Cuales for their unending care and love that inspire her a lot to pursue this study;

To all great and wonderful people whose names do not appear above for whatever assistance extended with sincerity, a million thanks to each one of you.

REFERENCES

- Arpilleda, A. J. (2021). Strategic intervention material: A tool in enhancing grade nine students' mathematical performance. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 10(5), DOI: 10.5861/ijrse.2021.5051.
- Antiporda, M (2014) The Performance of the learners NAT (2005-2015)
- Bundang & Parangal (2022). Teacher-Made Strategic Intervention Materials for Students with Learning Difficulties in Mathematics 8 in the Philippines. *International Journal of Advances in Interdisciplinary Research*, 2(10), 15-24.
- Department of Education (2005) DepEd Memorandum No. 117 series 2015. Training and Workshop on Strategic Intervention for Successful Learning.
- Department of Education (2019, August 22) DepEd Order no. 21 s. 2019: Policy Guidelines on the K to 12 Basic Education
- Department of Education (2013) Republic Act No. 10533 An act Enhancing the Basic Education Act of 1982, Strengthening Implementation and for other purposes.
- Estacio (2015) Development and Validation of a Learning Assessment Tool and Instructional Material https://www.academia.edu/23726543/Development_and_Validation_o

- f_a_Learning_Assessment_Tool_and_Instructional_Material_in_Physics_1_Mechanics
- Firestone (2016) Extent of Readiness of Grade 10 Students for General Mathematics of Senior High School in Sorsogon City, Philippines
- Department of Education (2015) Republic Act No. 10533 An act Enhancing the Basic Education Act of 1982 adopts the enclosed Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program.
- Sinco, M. G. (2018). Strategic Intervention Materials: A Tool in Improving Students' Academic Performance.https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352132094_STRATEGIC_INTERVENTION_MATERIALS_Strategic_Intervention_Materials_A_Tool_in_Improving_Students'_Academic_Performance
- Sinco, M. G. M., Futralan, M. C. Z., & Comighud, S. M. (2020, May). Strategic Intervention Materials: A Tool in Improving Students' Academic Performance. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3870630>
- PISA Program for International Student Assessment (2018) Results of ranking of Countries participating in PISA
- Suarez, M. G., & Casinillo, L. (2020). Effect of Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) on Academic Performance: Evidence from Students Of Science<https://www.ijsr.net/archive/v9i7/SR20706115116.pdf>
- Toquero (2020) SIMS as Intervention in Enriching the Teaching of Fundamental Operations in Mathematics:
<https://scimatic.org/storage/journals/11/pdfs/624.pdf>
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